

The Function of Association as A Community Empowerment Process in Independent Food Village Program (DEMAPAN)

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1

Abstract--- *Counseling function is to bridge the gap between the practices that are usually carried out by the target (farmers) with the knowledge and technology that always develops into the needs of the target. The counseling function is referred to as a link that outlines the process of delivering science and technology from its source to the people who need it. The function of the counseling system includes: facilitating the learning process, easy access, improving leadership abilities, developing the organization, analyzing and solving problems. Community empowerment is the concept of economic development that encapsulates the values of society to build a new paradigm in people-centered, participatory, empowerment and sustainable development. This research was conducted in Tegalsari Village, Plered District, Cirebon Regency. Held from July 2018 to January 2019, the aim was to find out the counseling function of the community empowerment process in the DEMAPAN program with a sample of 60 farmers. The method research that used in this research is descriptive and quantitative research, which aims to describe the symptoms that occur during the study. The researched variable include the counseling function variable and the community empowerment process in the DEMAPAN program activities. To find out the researched variable, descriptive data analysis was used with primary and secondary data, multiple linear regression analysis, and the F test and the t-test (two different test average paired samples). The results showed that the counseling function variable had a significant effect on the process of community empowerment in the DEMAPAN program, as evidenced from the results of the analysis obtained a value of T_{count} of $7.492 > F_{table} 4.013$, with a significance value of $0.002 < 0.005$. This shows that the better counseling function variable of the five indicators is learning process facilities, easy access, improving leadership skills, developing organizations, analyzing and solving problems will be followed by increasing community empowerment in the DEMAPAN program.*

Keywords--- *Counseling Function, Empowerment, DEMAPAN Program.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural counseling is an important and strategic activity that cannot be separated from development in the agricultural sector. Counseling activities in agricultural development act as a bridge that connects the practices carried out by farmers with agricultural knowledge and technology that is always developing. For farmers to practices that support farming, farmers need information and innovation in agriculture. Such information and innovations can be obtained by farmers from Field Agricultural Instructors (PPL) through the implementation of agricultural extension activities [1].

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Agricultural counseling in Indonesia has a long history, which began in the early 20th century. Agricultural counseling began with the need to increase agricultural output, both for colonialist interests and to meet indigenous needs. The need to increase agricultural production is calculated will be fulfilled if the advanced technologies found by experts can be practiced by farmers as primary producers. With quite encouraging results, these efforts continued to be developed and later established an institutionalized agricultural extension system in Indonesia with the establishment of the Extension Service (Landbouw Voorlichting Diensten or LVD) in 1908 under the Ministry of Agriculture [2], [3].

The function of counseling is to bridge the gap between the usual practice of the target and the knowledge and technology that always develops into the target's needs. The counseling function is referred to as a connector that explains the process of delivering science and technology from its source to the people who shape it. The function of the extension system includes: (a) facilitating the learning process (b) easy access (c) increasing leadership abilities (d) developing the organization and (e) analyzing and solving problems [4].

Today, the global society will always continue to face a food crisis, therefore, through a global agreement as outlined in the MDG's (Millennium Development Goals), an agenda for poverty and poverty reduction has been agreed to lead for a prosperous society. Efforts to realize the improvement of people's welfare are carried out through economic development based on competitive advantage, a wealth of natural resources, human resources, and national culture. These efforts require the support of mastery of science and technology which is increasing, one of which is through the process of empowerment[5].

Community empowerment is often difficult to distinguish from community development because it refers to overlapping notions of use in the community. In this study, community empowerment and community development are intended as community empowerment deliberately done by the government to facilitate local communities in planning, deciding and managing their resources, so that ultimately they have the ability and independence economically, ecologically and socially sustainable. Therefore, community empowerment is in essence closely related to sustainable development which requires the pre-requisites of community economic, ecological and social sustainability that are always dynamic. While agricultural development is a process of change that is better for improving the standard of living and welfare of the community, especially the farming community.

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Community empowerment is a concept of economic development that encapsulates social values. Community empowerment is an effort to improve the dignity of the people who are unable to escape the pitfalls of poverty and underdevelopment. In other words, empowerment is enabling and empowering the community. Efforts to empower people can be seen from three sides, First, creating an atmosphere or climate that allows the potential for developing community. Second, to strengthen the potential or power of the community. Third, empowering also means protecting[6]

Counseling is a process of empowerment, will produce a dynamic and progressive community sustainably, counseling has the main goal that is not limited to the creation of better farming, better business, better living, but to facilitate the community (beneficiaries) to adopt production and marketing strategies to accelerate the occurrence changes in social, political and economic conditions so that they can improve their personal and community living standards [7]. Counseling as a process of community empowerment is a process of community independence. Selfreliance is not patronizing but requires the active role of all parties who will receive benefits, especially from the target group itself [7].

The Independent Food Village (DEMAPAN) aims is to improve the ability of villagers in developing productive businesses based on local resources, increasing food availability, increasing purchasing power and accessing household food, to meet household nutritional adequacy. Villagers are still experiencing food insecurity so that purchasing power and access to food are very minimal plus income is also relatively small. So that special handling is needed to address this problem so that it can be resolved with encouragement and assistance from the government through an empowerment program to stimulate the community to explore the existing local potential to be used as a source of livelihood towards prosperity. The conditions above illustrate that food crop farming still has prospects for development. This prospect is supported by the availability of natural resources and high food needs.

The problem with the function of the counseling system in the research location is the low facilitation of the learning process, low access, low leadership ability, low organizational growth, and low analysis and problemsolving. Problems in the counseling function in the prosperous fish market are lack of counseling equipment such as information, unavailability of special places for counseling, limited sources of information, lack of confidence to act because of risks, lack of good governance, lack of responsiveness to opportunities and challenges. The purpose of this study was to determine the function of counseling on the process of community empowerment in the DEMAPAN program.

BI. DATA COLLECTION

The study was conducted in Tegalsari Village, Plered District, Cirebon Regency. This research was conducted in July 2018 until January 2019. As the object of research is farmers who received DEMAPAN program assistance with 60 respondents.

The research design uses descriptive quantitative methods using a questionnaire as a tool to find out information from respondents [8]. The descriptive research method is a method in examining the status of a group of people, an object, a condition, a system of thought or a class of events in the present [9]. The purpose of this descriptive study is to make a systematic, factual and accurate descriptive, picture or illustration of the facts, properties, and relationships of the phenomenon under investigation. The data used in this research are primary data (through interviews and questionnaires) and secondary data. The analytical method used in this research is the data validity test, reliability test, multiple linear analysis, t-test analysis, F test analysis and determinant coefficient[10].

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Analysis of the Extension Function Variable (X)

To find out the number of respondents who agreed or not in expressing their opinions through a questionnaire, in each indicator, there is an expectation score and a reality score, where the real score is the number of scores that exist on the indicator that has been studied, and the expected score is the number of respondents multiplied by the highest

score 1 - 5, that is 5, the number of real scores and expectations on the counseling function variable can be seen through the following table:

Table 1. Expectancy Scores and Reality Scores of Counseling Functions (X)

No.	Counseling Function (X)	Score		Percentage		Category
		Expectation	Reality	%		
1	Learning Process Facilities	1.120	903	80,63	Good	
2	Improving Leadership Abilities	840	691	82,26	Very Good	
3	Growing The Organization	1.120	949	84,73	Very Good	
4	Analyzing And Solving Problems	840	643	76,55	Good	
5		560	481	85,89	Very Good	
Amount		4.480	3.667	82,01	Very Good	

Sources: Primary data analysis results

Based on the results of the analysis of table 1 can be explained as follows:

1. Learning process facilities are classified in the Good category with a score of 80.63%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents who have been done shows the group members' assessment of the learning process is carried out routinely according to the specified schedule, the delivery of material is done clearly and easily understood by members, props needed in learning are always available, a place for learning is held on the spot members can reach. According to Mardikanto (1995), agricultural counseling is a process of behavior change through education, which is a change in behavior that is motivated by (a) understanding knowledge about everything that is valued better or beneficial to himself, his family, and the community, (b) his own will without coercion or any other party be it family, relatives, neighbors, friends or authorities, and (c) the ability to do something and provide the resources (input) needed for a change to occur.

This is in line with the research results of Unang Yunasaf et al. (2012) the role of instructors in the learning process of dairy farmers in KSU Tandangsari Sumedang, the results of the study showed that the role of counseling workers in facilitating the learning process of dairy farmers in Tandangsari KSU was mostly 56.67 % is classified as sufficient, while the remaining 20.00% is high, and 23.33% is classified as low. Counselors are judged by the breeder have enough roles in the role of educators as well as facilitators.

2. Ease of access classified in the category of Very good with a score of 82.26%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents showed that group members easily obtain material from official and trusted sources, technology can be reached, and easy to use by members. Counseling is very good in helping members to access information sources, access to production facilities and access to coaching. According to Rosnita (2014), ease of access is an educational process carried out by counseling agents aiming to make it easier for farmers to access information, technology, and other resources so that they can develop their businesses. This is in line with the results of research

by Ahmed Awad Talb Altalb, et al (2015) the role of agricultural counseling in the transfer and adoption of agricultural technology, the results of the study show that agricultural counseling agents have an effective and important role in helping farmers solve agricultural problems, agricultural counseling agent is the basis for the development of the agricultural sector, and without agricultural counseling, there is no benefit from modern agricultural techniques and information on modern agriculture. Improving leadership ability is classified in the category of Very good with a score of 84.73%. According to Haryanto (2010) states, voluntary theorists tend to view leadership as coercion or insistence on influence indirectly and as a means to form groups by the wishes of the leader.

3. Growing and developing organizations classified in the Good category with a score of 76.55%. Based on the results of existing research in the field shows that the collaboration of fellow members can improve the ability to run a productive business and by what is desired. Counseling is already good in developing member organizations, especially in developing group farmer organizations into productive organizations that can manage resources sustainably. According to Assauri (2008) to develop an organization that is through an organization people are continuously able to develop their capacity including farmers to create the results they want, where new mindsets are fostered; group aspirations are given freedom by existing provisions, and people are continuously learning to learn something together.
4. Analyzing and solving problems classified in the category of Very Good with a score of 85.89%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents showed that in analyzing and solving problems indirectly help group members to benefit, and solve problems that occur and be able to face the challenges that exist. The instructor has been very good at helping to solve the members' problems, a role that is felt by members, especially in fostering members and overcoming the limitations of their assets. According to Slavin (2011) problem solving is an attempt to overcome obstacles that impede the path to solutions. We find many problems in our daily lives, so we will create ways to respond, choose, test the responses we can to solve a problem.

This is in line with the results of research by Jock R. Anderson and Gershon Feder (2004) *Agricultural Counseling: Good Intention and Hard Reality*, the results of the study indicate that agricultural counseling can play an important role in development. The good public character of counseling agent underpins extensive public investment in counseling services. But although public counseling organizations are common in developing countries, they are often not adequately funded and their effectiveness is limited by many administrative and design shortcomings and links.

Based on Table 1 it's known that the extension function variable (X) gets a real score of 3,667 and an expectation score of 4,480 with a very good category (82.01%) this shows that in the counseling function group members can improve the learning process, increase ease of access, improve ability leadership, grow the organization, analyze and solve problems. According to Achmad Faqih (2016), the function of counseling is to bridge the gap between the practices that are usually carried out by the target with the knowledge and technology that always develops into the needs of the target. The counseling function is referred to as a liaison that outlines the process of delivering science and technology from its source to the people who shape it.

This is in line with the results of research Koyenikan, M. J. (2008) *Problems of Agricultural Counseling Policy in Nigeria*, the results of the study indicate that agricultural counseling is very important for development in the agricultural sector and national development as a whole.

Descriptive Analysis of the Community Empowerment Process Variable (Y)

To find out the number of respondents who agreed or not in expressing their opinions through a questionnaire, in each indicator, there is an expectation score and a reality score, where the real score is the number of scores that exist on the indicator that has been studied, and the expected score is the number of respondents multiplied by the highest score 1 - 5, that is 5, the number of real scores and expectations on the community empowerment process variables can be seen through the following table 2:

Table 2. Expectation Scores and Reality Scores for Community Empowerment Processes (Y)

No	Community Empowerment Process (Y)	Score		Percentage %	Category
		Expectations	Reality		
1	Enabling	560	417	74,46	Good
2	Empowering	560	386	68,93	Good
3	Protecting	560	457	81,61	Very Good
Amount		1.680	1.260	75,00	Good

Source: Primary data analysis results, 2019.

1. Enabling

Enabling is in the Good category with a score of 74.46%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents showed that the existence of community empowerment activities can motivate to develop fish processing businesses, with the potential of communities that can still be developed can rise the enthusiasm in running their business. Empowerment must be able to free people from structural and cultural barriers that are inhibiting. According to Huraerah [11] enabling is to create an atmosphere or climate that enables the potential of the community to develop optimally.

This is in line with the research results of suryaningsum et all[12] the effectiveness of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in PT Pertamina, the perspective of community empowerment in Cilacap Regency. This showed that the results are real for the surrounding community. In the initial stages the assistance received repaired the posyandu building and gradually continued to grow. This is an indication that Pertamina has been able to activate posyandu activities. Puspa Ayu Posyandu which was previously a normal posyandu, has now become a Posyandu Model that has integrated several posyandu activities such as Pos Paud, BKB, PHBS, and also health services.

2. Empowering

Empowering is classified in the Good category with a score of 68.93%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents showed that with community empowerment can increase capacity and strengthen their potential, with the empowerment of the community can open access opportunities. Empowerment must be able to grow and develop all the abilities and confidence of the community that supports independence. According to Slamet and Wajdi[13], [14] empowering is strengthening the knowledge and abilities possessed by natural communities to solve problems and meet their needs.

3. Protecting

Protecting is in the Very good category with a score of 81.61%. Based on the results of interviews with respondents showed that the process of empowerment must be prevented the weak become increasingly weak, because of a lack of empowerment in the face of the strong. Empowerment must be directed at the elimination of all types of discrimination and domination that do not benefit small communities, empowerment must protect the weak, minority and isolated communities. This is in line with the results of research by Mohammad Sadegh Allahyari[15], redefining the purpose of agricultural counseling towards sustainability in Iran, the results of the study show that the Iranian counseling system should be considered as a development goal as important as increasing social capital. Among the objectives, empowerment, and enhancement of food security have the highest priority for the counseling system towards sustainability. It should be noted that other objectives must also be considered at a high level. This shows that having multigoals is very important for the success of the counseling system towards sustainability.

Based on Table 2 it is known that the variable of community empowerment process (Y) gets a real score of 1,260 and an expected score of 1,680 with a good category (75.00%) this shows that in the process of community empowerment group members can create an atmosphere/climate that allows the potential of its members to develop, able to increase capacity by strengthening the potential or power possessed by its members, and protecting interests by developing a protection system for members. According to Fahrudin [16], community empowerment is an effort to enable and empower the community.

This is in line with the results of research Indri, et al [17] (2016) the role and performance of agricultural counseling agents in empowering laying hens breeder in Jember Regency results showed that the role of counseling agents influence empiric empowerment empirically proved significant. The better the role of counseling agents will affect the empowerment of farmers in Jember Regency.

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Simple linear regression analysis is to test the effect of the Extension Function variable on the Community Empowerment Process. This model assumes a one-line / linear relationship between the dependent variable and each of its predictors. In calculating a simple linear regression analysis here using IBM SPSS version 22.0 for Windows.

With the following analysis results.

1. Test F

The F test in simple linear regression analysis is used to find out whether the extension function variable influences the process of community empowerment. Tests carried out using significance level 0.05 (= 5%).

Analysis of the F Test was calculated using the help of IBM SPSS version 22.0 for Windows.

Table 3. F test results

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	113.873	1	113.873	61.987	.000 ^b
	Residual	106.001	58	2.305		
	Total	219.874	59			

a. Dependent Variable: Community Empowerment

a. Predictors: (Constant), Counseling Function

Seen from Table 3 shows that the F Test is used to test the independent variables on the dependent variable. This test is done by comparing the value of Fcount with Ftable, the result of the test is that Fcount shows a value of 61.987 so $F_{count} > F_{table}$ 4.013 or $Sig F < 5\%$ (0.000 < 0.05). This means that the extension function variable (X) significantly influences the community empowerment process variable (Y). In the counseling function variable, five indicators affect, among others, learning process facilities, easy access, improving leadership skills, developing organizations, analyzing and solving problems, where if the five indicators are carried out well, the process of community empowerment in the processing program will increase. The learning process in counseling is not only interpreted as an incidental learning activity to solve the problem being faced but more importantly is the growth and development of a long-life learning spirit independently and continuously. According to Achmad Faqih and wajdi [4], [18] the function of counseling is to bridge the gap between the practices that are usually carried out by the target with the knowledge and technology that always develops into the needs of the target. The counseling function is referred to as a liaison that outlines the process of delivering science and technology from its source to the people who shape it.

This is in line with the results of Akhter Ali's study [19], the impact of agricultural counseling services on technology adoption and yields: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan, the results of the study show that agricultural counseling services in Pakistan play an important role related to the adoption of laser leveling technology. Laser leveling is becoming a very important new technology in conserving water and improving soil texture and structure. The most important and positive impact of agricultural counseling services is on rice and wheat yields in Pakistan. This increase in crop yields can directly help increase household income and reduce poverty levels that are urgently needed in Pakistan. Overall agricultural counseling plays an important positive role but there are still many improvements that can be made. Probit estimates also show that most large farmers currently benefit from agricultural counseling services and counseling services for small farmers need to be provided.

2. Test t

The t-test was used to find out the significant effect between the independent variables on the dependent variable.

The basis for decision making used in the t-test is as follows:

- a. There is no significant effect if the significance value ≥ 0.05 that H_0 is accepted. States that the independent variable has no significant effect on the dependent variable.
- b. There is a significant effect if the significance value < 0.05 ie that is rejected. Stating that the independent variable has a significant effect on the dependent variable.

In calculating the t-test analysis here using IBM SPSS version 22.0 for Windows. Table

4. Test Results t

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	7.791	2.299		3.498	.001
	Counseling Function	.261	.034	.727	7.492	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Community Empowerment

Source : : IBM SPSS version 22,0 for Windows

Based on Table 22 above, it shows that the results of t-test for the counseling function variable (X) obtained t value of 7.492, using the significance limit $\alpha = 0.05$, obtained a sig t value of 0.001 < 0.005, thus the t-test hypothesis of the counseling function variable (X) has an influence on the community empowerment process variable (Y).

Based on the results of the simple regression analysis in table 22 the equation can be formed into: Y = 7.791 + 0.261X

Information :

X = counseling function

Y = community empowerment process

The equation shows a constant value of 7.791 that if the counseling function has a value of 0 then community empowerment in the community empowerment program in DEMAPAN has a value of 7.791. The counseling function has a value of 0.261 indicating positive and significant results on the process of community empowerment in the community empowerment program DEMAPAN.

Based on the above results, the counseling agents carried out by the instructor in the fish processing program are good so that the members of the prosperous fish randegan that apply the empowerment of the DEMAPAN program community by the instructor members are more empowered, in addition to that there are facilities in a good learning process one of them with teaching aids adequate and also ease of access provided by instructors to members so that the public is increasingly interested in the programs provided by counseling agents.

This is in line with the results of research Indri, et al (2016) which states that the counseling function in empowering laying hens breeders significantly influences this can be seen from the performance of good counseling agents so the breeders can innovate in increasing the production of laying hens. According to Mario, et al (2015) that if initially the instructor was emphasized on guidance for the breeders in a better business, it turned into pressure on technology experts who worked on breeders so that the breeders could increase productivity and production.

VI. STUDY RESULTS, SUMMARY AND CONTRIBUTION

The counseling function variable significantly affected the process of community empowerment in the DEMAPAN program, as evidenced from the analysis results obtained a Tcount value of 7.492 > Ftable 4.013, with a significance value of 0.002 < 0.005. This shows that the better counseling function variable of the five indicators, namely the learning process facilities, easy access, improving leadership skills, developing organizations, analyzing and solving problems will be followed by increasing community empowerment in the DEMAPAN program.

From the research results, it is known that the indicator of organizational development has the smallest value of the other indicators so it is expected that counseling agents will increase their interest in developing and developing the organization so that the counseling function in the community empowerment process in the processing program is even better

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